

Strengthening local and thematic DCCs: setting up new local and regional centres

Call for proposals

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1 Introduction

In this Call for proposals information is provided about the application procedure for the “Strengthening local and thematic DCCs: setting up new local and regional centres” funding round. This Call for proposals falls under the responsibility of Open Science NL, part of the Dutch Research Council (NWO).

In this Call for proposals you will find information about the aim of this programme (Chapter 2), the conditions for the grant application (Chapter 3) and how your proposal will be assessed (Chapter 4). This is the information you need to submit a grant application. Chapter 5 states the obligations for grant recipients in the event you are awarded funding. Chapter 6 contains the contact details and Chapter 7 the annexes.

1.1 Background

The Dutch government has made available substantial funding to support the transition to open science in the Netherlands. The aim of the investment is to make open science the norm. Open Science NL was set up to take responsibility for the allocation of these funds. Open Science NL is part of NWO.

This Call for proposals is launched in addition to the instruments announced in the first work programme of Open Science NL, which covers the years 2024-2025. All financial instruments of Open Science NL cover the following priority areas:

1. Capacity building,
2. Infrastructure for Open Science,
3. Robust research processes,
4. Evidence base for Open Science,
5. Empowering communities.

The Call for proposals “Strengthening local and thematic DCCs: setting up new local and regional centres” falls under the priority area “Capacity building”. Investing in capacity building for open science is one of the essential requirements for putting open science into practice. Capacity building refers here to the process of enhancing the organisational or community-based knowledge, skills and abilities needed to adopt open science practices effectively. In other words, capacity building refers to investment in people and their skills. Capacity building initiatives provide much needed training and support to navigate the technical, legal, social, cultural and ethical aspects of open science, thereby enabling communities to overcome barriers and embrace new approaches. Ultimately, capacity building strengthens the foundations of sustainable open science ecosystems, which encompass not only specific research outputs (publications, data, software and non-traditional research output, such as creative works, policy reports, etc.), but also research processes, infrastructures and research cultures.

Hoofdstuk 1: **Introduction** / Versterken lokale en thematische DCC's: opzetten nieuwe lokale en regionale centra

In the past few years, NWO and Open Science NL have already been investing in capacity building at the institutional level, mainly through calls to support digital competence centres: Local Digital Competence Centres (LDCCs)¹ and Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDCCs). The local and thematic DCCs already form a network of digital competence centres². Through this Call for proposals Open Science NL wishes to further expand this network with new competence centres.

1.2 Available budget

The available budget for this Call for proposals is €2,000,000. Within this Call for proposals it is expected that a maximum of three proposals will be awarded funding.

1.3 Submission deadline(s)

The deadline for submitting full proposals is 28 January 2025, before 14:00:00 CET.

When you submit your application in ISAAC, you will also need to enter some details online. Therefore please start submitting your application at least one day before the deadline of this Call for proposals. Applications that are submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration.

¹ There are 23 Local Digital Competence Centres in the Netherlands. They are established at the following institutions: Erasmus University Rotterdam, Leiden University, Maastricht University, Radboud University, Tilburg University, TU Delft, TU Eindhoven, University of Amsterdam, University of Groningen, University of Twente, Utrecht University, VU Amsterdam, Wageningen University & Research, Amsterdam UMC, Erasmus MC, Leiden UMC, Maastricht UMC+, Radboud UMC, UMC Groningen, UMC Utrecht. There is one LDCC each for the KNAW Institutes, the NWO Institutes and the Universities of Applied Sciences.

² DCC NL Implementation Network: https://lcrdm.nl/?page_id=216

2 Aim

This chapter describes the aim of the programme.

2.1 Aim of the programme

The purpose of this Call for proposals is to provide impulse funding to institutions, which have not yet received funding from NWO or Open Science NL for building or strengthening digital competence centres.

A digital competence centre (DCC) is a local, regional and thematic expertise centre in an area of research data management, open research software and computation, with a strong focus on open science. A DCC provides support to research communities and helps increase digital competencies within research communities.

Example of tasks and activities of a DCC might include the following³:

- Supporting researchers (locally, regionally, thematically) by helping them increase their digital competencies (e.g. through training, advice, practical support, development and provision of tools and services).
- Helping researchers connect with relevant infrastructures and get access to relevant instruments and services.
- Raising awareness about research data management, open research software and open science.
- Participation in existing local and thematic DCC networks in order to exchange knowledge and to facilitate collaboration.

In addition to the tasks listed above, a DCC can also perform tasks which are specific to the nature of the communities they support. The applicants have to explain in the proposals their strategy for using the available investment in order to build or strengthen their digital competence centre.

Furthermore, the applicants have to explain their concrete plans to sustain the additional capacity in the long-term and to embed it within the existing organisational structures.

³ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/news/digital-competence-centers-knowledge-institutions-forging-ahead>

3 Conditions for applicants

This chapter contains the conditions that are applicable to your grant application. Firstly it describes who can apply for funding (Section 3.1) and what you can request funding for (Section 3.2). Subsequently, you will find the conditions for preparing and submitting the application (Sections 3.3 and 3.4) and the specific funding conditions (Section 3.5).

3.1 Who can apply

Applications for funding to build or strengthen a DCC (see chapter 2.1) can be submitted exclusively by door individuals acting on behalf of the board of the following organisations, which have not previously received funding from NWO or Open Science NL for this purpose, namely:

- the Open University in Heerlen, as described in the appendix of the law on higher education and research (WHW⁴), under h;
- the philosophical (religious) universities as described in the appendix of the WHW, under i;
- the universities in the Caribbean region of the Netherlands, as explained in the policy regulation of the Universities in the Kingdom of the Netherlands⁵.

Persons with a zero-hour employment agreement may not submit a proposal.

Additional conditions:

- All four philosophical (religious) universities, as well as all the universities in the Caribbean region of the Kingdom of the Netherlands can submit only one proposal, for only one DCC each.
- Applications have to be signed by the applicant and by the Executive Board of the organisation.
- A maximum of one application can be submitted per organisation.

3.1.1 Main- and co-applicants

The main applicant submits the proposal via the NWO web application ISAAC. During the assessment process, NWO will communicate with the main applicant.

After a proposal has been awarded funding, the main applicant will become the project leader and point of contact for NWO. The knowledge institution of the main applicant is the main beneficiary and will become the official secretary.

Co-applicants have an active role in realising the project. The (sub)project leaders and beneficiary/beneficiaries are jointly responsible for realising the entire project.

3.2 What can be applied for

Per project, a grant amount of at most €1,000,000.00 can be applied for. The maximum duration of the proposed project is 4 years. The applicant can include costs for personnel and materials. The available budget modules (including the maximum amounts) are listed below. Apply only for funding that is vital to realise the project. The rates and an explanation of these budget modules are given in annex 7.1.

⁴ Wet op het hoger onderwijs en wetenschappelijk onderzoek: <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0005682/2024-09-01>

⁵ <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0050167/2024-08-31>

The project submitted by the Open University, as well as the joint project proposal submitted by the four philosophical (religious) universities can be for a maximum of €500,000.00 each. The joint project proposal submitted by the universities in the Caribbean region of the Kingdom of the Netherlands can be for a maximum of €1,000,000.00.

3.2.1 Personnel

Funding may be requested for salary costs of personnel contributing to the project. The amount depends on the type of appointment and the organisation where the personnel is employed.

3.2.2 Material

Funding may be requested for all project-specific material costs. There is no maximum percentage of these costs in relation to the total budget requested.

3.3 Preparing an application

The steps involved in writing your application are:

- download the application form from the NWO web application ISAAC or from the NWO web page (on the grant page of the funding instrument concerned);
- complete the application form;
- save the application form in ISAAC as a PDF file and upload it with any compulsory annexes;
- fill in the requested information online in ISAAC.

Compulsory annex:

- budget.

The appendix must be drawn up in accordance with the template provided by NWO. Annexes must be uploaded in ISAAC separately from the application. The budget must be submitted in ISAAC as an Excel file. All of the other annexes, except for the budget, must be submitted as PDF files (without encryption). Any annexes other than those stated above are not permitted.

You must write your application in English.

An application can only be submitted via the web application ISAAC. Applications that are not submitted via ISAAC will not be taken into consideration.

As the main applicant, you are required to submit the application via your own personal ISAAC account.

It is important to start with your application in ISAAC on time:

- if you do not yet have an ISAAC account, then you should create this on time to prevent any possible registration problems;
- any new research organisations must also be added to ISAAC by NWO;
- you also need to submit other details online.

Applications submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration by NWO.

For technical questions, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk, see contact (Chapter 6).

Applicants are expected to have informed the research organisation where they work about submitting the application and that the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this Call for proposals.

3.4 Conditions for submission

3.4.1 Formal conditions for submission

NWO will assess your application against all the conditions set out in this Call for proposals, including the conditions listed below. Your application will only be admitted to the assessment procedure if it meets these conditions. After submitting your application, NWO requests you to be available to implement any possible administrative corrections so that you can (still) meet the conditions for submission.

These conditions are:

- the main applicant and co-applicant(s) meet the conditions stated in Section 3.1;
- the application complies with the DORA guidelines as described in Section 4.1;
- the application is submitted via the main applicant's ISAAC account;
- the application is received before the deadline;
- the application is written in English;
- the application budget is drawn according to the terms of this Call for proposals (using the format made available which includes the most recent rates);
- the proposed project has a duration of maximum 4 years;
- all required annexes, after a possible request for additions or changes, have been completed and submitted completely and according to the instructions and in accordance with the terms of this Call for proposals.

3.5 Conditions on granting

The [NWO Grant Rules](#) are applicable to all applications.

3.5.1 Compliance with the National Knowledge Security Guidelines

World-class science can benefit from international cooperation. The National Knowledge Security Guidelines (hereafter: the Guidelines) helps knowledge institutions to ensure that international cooperation can take place securely. Knowledge security concerns the undesirable transfer of sensitive knowledge and technology that compromises national security; the covert influence of state actors on education and research, which jeopardises academic freedom and social safety; and ethical issues that may arise in cooperation with countries that do not respect fundamental rights.

Applicants are responsible for ensuring that their project complies and will continue to comply with the Guidelines. By submitting an application, the applicant commits to the recommendations stipulated in these Guidelines. In the event of a suspected breach of the Guidelines in an application submitted to NWO for project funding, or in a project funded by NWO, NWO may ask the applicant to provide a risk assessment demonstrating that the recommendations in the Guidelines have been taken into consideration. If the applicant fails to comply with NWO's request, or if the risk assessment is in apparent breach of the Guidelines, this may affect NWO's grant award or decision-making process. NWO may also include further conditions in the award letter if appropriate.

The National Knowledge Security Guidelines can be found on the central government website at: [Home | National Contact Point for Knowledge Security \(loketkennisveiligheid.nl\)](#).

3.5.2 Scientific integrity

In accordance with the NWO Grant Rules, the project that NWO funds must be carried out in accordance with the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2018). By submitting the proposal, the applicant commits to this code. In the case of a (possible) violation of these standards during a project funded by NWO, the applicant should immediately inform NWO of this and should submit all relevant documents to NWO. More information about the code of conduct and the policy regarding research integrity can be found on the website: [Scientific integrity | NWO](#).

3.5.3 Ethical statement or licence

The applicant is responsible for determining whether an ethical statement or licence is needed for the realisation of the proposed project. The applicant should ensure that this is obtained from the relevant institution or ethics committee on time. The absence or presence of an ethical statement or licence at the time of the application process has no effect on the assessment of the application. If the project is awarded funding, then the grant is issued under the condition that the necessary ethical statement or licence is obtained before the latest start date for the project. The project cannot start until NWO has received a copy of the ethical statement or license.

3.5.4 Nagoya Protocol

The Nagoya Protocol ensures an honest and reasonable distribution of benefits emerging from the use of genetic resources (Access and Benefit Sharing; ABS). Researchers who make use of genetic sources from the Netherlands or abroad for their research should familiarise themselves with the Nagoya Protocol ([Home - ABS Focal Point](#)). NWO assumes that researchers will take all necessary actions with respect to the Nagoya Protocol.

4 Assessment procedure

This chapter first describes the assessment according to the DORA principles (Section 4.1) and the course of the assessment procedure (Section 4.2). Second, it states the criteria that the assessment committee will use to assess your application (Section 4.3).

The NWO Code for Dealing with Personal Interests applies to all persons and NWO employees involved in the assessment and/or decision-making process ([Code for Dealing with Personal Interests | NWO](#)).

NWO strives to achieve an inclusive culture where there is no place for conscious or unconscious barriers due to cultural, ethnic or religious background, gender, sexual orientation, health or age ([Diversity and inclusion | NWO](#)). NWO encourages members of the assessment committee to be actively aware of implicit associations and to try to minimise these. NWO will provide them with information about concrete ways of improving the assessment of an application.

4.1 De San Francisco Declaration (DORA)

NWO is a signatory to the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). DORA is a worldwide initiative that aims to improve the way research and researchers are assessed. DORA contains recommendations for research funders, research institutions, scientific journals and other parties.

DORA aims to reduce the uncritical use of bibliometric indicators and obviate unconscious bias in the assessment of research and researchers. DORA's overarching philosophy is that research should be evaluated on its own merits rather than on the basis of surrogate measures, such as the journal in which the research is published.

When assessing the scientific track record of applicants, NWO makes use of a broad definition of scientific output.

NWO requests committee members not to rely on indicators such as the Journal Impact Factor or the h-index when assessing applications. Applicants are not allowed to mention these in their applications. You are, however, allowed to list other scientific products besides publications, such as datasets, patents, software and code, et cetera.

For more information on how NWO is implementing the principles of DORA, see [DORA | NWO](#).

4.2 Procedure

The application procedure consists of the following steps:

- submission of the proposal;
- admissibility of the proposal;
- initial advice from the assessment committee;
- rebuttal;
- assessment committee meeting;
- decision-making.

An external, independent assessment committee will be assigned for this Call for proposals, consisting of representatives from science and practice with knowledge of the field.

The task of the assessment committee is to assess the applications and the relevant documents that are submitted, in conjunction with each other and with regard to both the respective merits of each application and the assessment criteria outlined in this Call for proposals.

Due to both the expertise present in the assessment committee, NWO has decided with regard to the assessment of these applications to exercise the option outlined in Article 2.2.4, paragraph 2, of the NWO Grant Rules, to assess all applications without involving referees.

4.2.1 Submission of a proposal

For the submission of the proposal, a standard form is available on the funding page of this Call for proposals on the NWO website. When you write your proposal, you must adhere to the questions stated on this form and the procedure given in the explanatory notes. You must also adhere to the conditions for the maximum number of words and pages.

Your complete application form must have been received before the deadline via ISAAC (see Section 1.3). After this deadline, you can no longer submit a proposal. After submitting the proposal, the main applicant will receive a confirmation of receipt.

4.2.2 Admissibility of the proposal

As soon as possible after you have submitted your proposal, you will hear from NWO whether or not your proposal will be taken into consideration. NWO will determine this based on several administrative-technical criteria (see the formal conditions for submission, Section 3.4). NWO can only take your proposal into consideration if it meets these conditions.

Please bear in mind that within two weeks after the submission deadline, NWO may approach you with any possible administrative corrections that need to be made so that your proposal can (still) meet the conditions for submission. You will be given one opportunity to make the corrections, and you will be given five working days to do this.

4.2.3 Pre-advice assessment committee

After this, your proposal will be submitted for comments to several members of the assessment committee (the pre-advisers). The pre-advisers will provide a written substantive and reasoned response to the proposal. They will formulate these comments based on the substantive assessment criteria (see Section 4.3.1) and will give the proposal a numerical score per assessment criterion. For this, the NWO score table will be used (on a scale of 1 to 9, where "1" is excellent and "9" unsatisfactory).

4.2.4 Rebuttal

The main applicant subsequently receives the anonymised pre-advice. You then have the opportunity to formulate a rebuttal. You will be given five working days to submit your rebuttal via ISAAC. If you decide to withdraw the proposal, then you should do this as quickly as possible by sending an email stating this to the office and withdrawing the proposal in ISAAC. If NWO receives your rebuttal after the deadline, then it will not be included in the rest of the procedure.

4.2.5 Meeting of the assessment committee

The committee will make its own assessment based on the available material. Although the pre-advice will 'guide' the final assessment to a large extent, it will not be blindly accepted without question by the committee. The committee will consider and compare the arguments of the pre-advisers (also amongst each other) and examine whether the rebuttal contains a well-formulated response to the critical comments from the pre-advice.

Following the discussion, the committee draws up a written recommendation addressed to Open Science NL Steering Board about the quality and ranking of the proposals. This recommendation is based on the assessment criteria. The proposal must receive an overall qualification of at least "good" to be eligible for funding. The proposal must also receive at least the qualification "good" for each of the individual assessment criteria.

For more information about the qualifications, see [Applying for funding, how does it work? | NWO](#).

4.2.6 Decision-making

Finally, Open Science NL Steering Board will assess the procedure followed as well as the advice from the assessment committee. They will subsequently determine the final qualifications and make a decision over awarding or rejecting the proposals.

4.2.7 Timetable

Below, you will find the timetable for this Call for proposals. During the current procedure, NWO might find it necessary to make further changes to the timetable for this Call for proposals. You will be informed about this in time.

28 January 2025 before 14:00:00 CET	Deadline proposals
February 2025	Pre-advisers consulted
February/March 2025	Applicants can submit a rebuttal
April 2025	Assessment committee meeting
May 2025	Decision Open Science NL Steering Board

4.3 Criteria

4.3.1 Substantive assessment criteria

The applications submitted within this Call for proposals will be substantially assessed on the basis of the following criteria:

1. Alignment with the scope of the Call for proposals (30%):
 - a. To what extent does the proposed project fit within the scope of this Call for proposals?
 - b. Is there a clear picture of the current situation around digital competences and open science, identification of gaps and an appropriate strategy to address these gaps?

Hoofdstuk 4: **Assessment** procedure / Versterken lokale en thematische DCC's: opzetten nieuwe lokale en regionale centra

2. Feasibility of the proposal (50%):
 - c. Are the plans for building or increasing digital competencies clear and realistic?
 - d. Have the relevant existing networks been correctly identified, and has a compelling plan to connect to them been drawn up?
 - e. Is there an analysis of risk factors and an adequate risk mitigation strategy?
 - f. Is the budget reasonable for the proposed work and sufficiently substantiated?
3. Sustainability plans (20%)
 - a. Are the plans for long-term sustainability appropriate and sufficiently realistic?

5 Obligations for grant recipients

This chapter details the various obligations that - in addition to the conditions stated in Section 3.5 - apply after funds have been awarded.

5.1 Intellectual property

With respect to intellectual property (IP), the NWO IP policy applies. This can be found in Chapter 4 of the NWO Grant Rules.

Applicants must carry out a project funded by NWO during the time that they work for the research organisation. If an applicant or a researcher funded by NWO is appointed by more than one employer, then the other employer should relinquish any possible IP rights that emerge from the project of the applicant.

5.2 Socially responsible licensing

The knowledge that emerges from the project could be suitable for use in society. When agreements about licensing and/or the transfer of research results developed under this Call for proposals are made, due consideration should be given to the ten principles for socially responsible licensing, as stated in the NFU factsheet "[Ten principles for Socially Responsible Licensing | NFU](#)".

5.3 Open Access

As a signatory to the Berlin Declaration (2003) and a member of cOAlition S (2018), NWO is committed to making the results of the research it funds openly accessible (Open Access). By doing this, NWO supports the ambitions of the Dutch government to make all publicly funded research available Open Access. Scientific publications arising from projects awarded on the basis of this Call for proposals must therefore be made available in Open Access form in accordance with the NWO Open Access Policy. For more detailed information about NWO's Open Access policy, see [Open Science | NWO](#).

Other outputs resulting from this Call for Proposals should also be shared as openly as possible, under an open licence. Examples of such outputs include presentations, reports, training materials, working papers and posters. It is advised that these outputs are shared via a trusted repository, such as the Zenodo platform which offers free storage.

6 Contact and other information

6.1 Contact

6.1.1 Specific questions

For administrative and procedural questions about this Call for proposals please contact:

Dr. Mark van Assem

Tel nr. +31(0)70 344 0915

Email: dccversterken@nwo.nl

For content questions about this Call for proposals please contact:

Dr. Marta Teperek (FAIR data)

Tel nr. +31(0)70 349 4282

Email: dccversterken@nwo.nl

6.1.2 Technical questions about the web application ISAAC

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Please read the manual first before consulting the helpdesk. The ISAAC helpdesk can be contacted from Monday to Friday between 10:00 and 17:00 hours on +31 (0)70 34 40 600. However, you can also submit your question by email to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will then receive an answer within two working days.

6.2 Overige informatie

The whole text of this Call for proposals has been published in both Dutch and English. The Dutch version is deemed authentic. For legal interpretation the text of the Dutch version will be decisive.

NWO processes data from applicants received in the context of this Call for proposals in accordance with the NWO Privacy Statement, [Privacy Statement | NWO](#).

NWO might approach applicants for an evaluation of the procedure and/or research programme.

7 Annexes

7.1 Budget modules and rates

7.1.1 Personnel

Funding can be requested for staff required for the implementation of the project. This may include roles such as data stewards, trainers, metadata and ontology experts, research software engineers, community managers, project leaders, etc. The staffing requirements should be described in the application. Use the rates according to the HOT tariffs, table 1, average direct labour costs per salary scale, column 'Hourly rate for productive hours, excluding VAT'. The salary scale determines the rate. When translating the internally used scales to HOT rates, choose the HOT scale that best matches the expected actual costs (excluding overhead costs).

The funding can be used for salary costs of existing staff (only for the time they work on this project), but also for newly appointed staff.

The duration of the appointment cannot exceed the duration of the project funded by NWO.

7.1.2 Material

Funding may be requested for all project-specific costs relating to, among others, consumables, purchase of services, materials, small instruments, access to (inter)national facilities, software and research resources that have no economic value after use. Travel and accommodation costs (national and international) for all people working on the project incl. foreign guest researchers, costs for the organisation of (international) workshops and symposia, costs of training and knowledge exchange (including facilitation of knowledge exchange and networking in order to develop knowledge and expertise within the DCC by organising or participating in workshops and events), costs for data management, publications, and costs in the context of citizen science also fall under this module.

Travel expenses (national and international) will only be reimbursed on the basis of second class/economy class fares. For publications, the provisions in Section 4.5 Open access apply. Costs for an audit statement can only be claimed for organisations that are not subject to OCW's education audit protocol for a maximum of €5,000 per audit statement.

It is not permitted to include costs for:

- organisational infrastructure and overhead, including a fully functioning workplace, accommodation, office automation, personnel administration, commuting expenses, training, facilities, HR advice and business care, documentary information provision and home office allowance;
- the use and maintenance of in-house developed scientific infrastructure;
- regular teaching activities;

7.2 Indexing

The rate at the time of the decision date applies. NWO will, if necessary, apply a one-off indexation of personnel costs when awarding the grant. The date on which the rates take effect is used for this purpose. If the date of publication of the fees is later than the effective date, the date of publication is used. The tariffs of the Universities of the Netherlands (UNL) usually take effect on 1 July, of the Dutch Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU) on 1 August and of the Government Tariffs Manual (HOT) on 1 January.

The on-off indexation does not affect the grant ceiling and the maximum grant amount to be applied for. The grant ceiling and maximum requestable grant amount remain unchanged during the assessment procedure. If awarded, one-off indexation will be applied to the grant amount.

If co-funding is required or permitted, the one-off indexation does not affect the requirements for own contributions and co-funding, nor the IP rights that may result from the co-funding

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Dutch Research Council

Visiting address:

Location The Hague

Laan van Nieuw Oost-Indië

2593 CE The Hague

Netherlands

Location Utrecht

Winthontlaan 2

3526 KV Utrecht

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